

EFFECTS OF POSTHARVEST LOSSES ON PROFITABILITY OF FRESH TOMATO MARKETERS IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The debate on post-harvest losses of vegetables, including fresh tomato, has taken a central position especially in developing countries, such as Nigeria. The effect of post-harvest losses on the profitability of tomato marketers has not been adequately investigated. This study examined the effect of Post-harvest losses on profitability of tomato marketers in Delta State, Nigeria. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected with questionnaire from sampled 150 tomato marketers in 5 Markets in Delta State, Nigeria. Collected data were analysed and stated objectives achieved using descriptive statistic (mean, percentage, charts), correlation model multiple regression model, profit function and Shepherd-Futrell efficiency model. The results of the study indicate that tomato marketers were mainly female 97%, with an average age of 43years, literate and members of cooperative societies (51%). Majority (66.0%) of the marketers operated long marketing channel. The result of the correlation analysis indicates that there was a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) and positive relationship between marketing channels and quantity of spoiled tomatoes. Cost of product spoilage indicated significant ($p \leq 0.05$) relationship with marketing channels of tomatoes in the study area. The result also shows a significant ($P \leq 0.05$) positive relationship between quantity of spoilage and cost of tomatoes spoilage. Given a Shepherd Futrell Efficiency Coefficient of 90% indicates a low marketing efficiency possibly due to postharvest losses. Test of hypothesis revealed that the quantity and value of post-harvest losses negatively and significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) affected the profitability of fresh tomato marketers. There was sufficient evidence to conclude that post-harvest losses must have been responsible for low return on investment (ROI) and low efficiency in fresh tomato marketing. It was recommended among others that volume of fresh tomato stocked/traded at a time should be effectively managed to reduce spoilage to the barest minimum.

KEYWORDS: Effects, postharvest losses, profitability, fresh tomato, marketers

INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) is a both a cash and food crop grown in the forest, transitional or derived savannah and savannah zones. With an annual total area of one million hectares is reportedly used for its cultivation, Nigeria ranked 12th in production with total output of 1,560,000mt in 2014 ([9]Babalola, et al., 2010; [7]Arah, 2014;). Tomato ranks high among high value food produce in Africa and Nigeria. [8]Ayandiji, et al. (2011) noted that fresh fruits such as tomatoes are very important sources of vitamins which are essential for healthy human diet; tomatoes are rich in minerals, vitamins, essential amino acids, sugars and dietary fibres, containing much vitamin B and C, iron and phosphorus. Tomatoes constitute a sizeable source of income for

farmers across the globe. [6]Aidoo, et al. (2014) indicated that tomato production is a source of livelihood and income for most farmers, distributors and marketers.

Vegetables like tomato are usually harvested when they are fresh and high in moisture content and are thus distinguished from field crops, which are harvested at the mature stage for grains, pulses, oil seeds or fibre. This high moisture content of such vegetables makes their handling, transportation and marketing a special problem particularly in the tropics ([19]Sablani et al., 2016).

Tomato postharvest losses can be attributed to a wide variety of factors, ranging from growing conditions to marketing channels.

According to [1]Acharya and Agarwal (2019) marketing channels are the routes through which agricultural products move from the point of production to the final point of consumption. Long distances from farms to markets as well as insufficient storage conditions can lead to losses to the tomato produce ([10]Chandy, 2011). A study by [9]Babalola et al. (2010) showed that the longer the distance from farm to the market, the greater the losses experienced due to congestion of the tomato fruits and the resultant build-up of heat. [15]Mujib et al. (2017) noted that marketing channel type and quantity traded of tomato played a vital role in postharvest losses. In Nigeria, attempts at explaining the underlying causes of postharvest losses in tomato production have largely remained in the realm of speculation and conjecture. However, empirical information on marketing channel as

one of the causes of these losses are required if solutions are to be found for this critical problem in tomato production. Therefore, this study was designed to examine the effect of post-harvest losses on profitability of fresh tomato marketers.

Marketing plays a critical role in meeting the overall goals of food security, poverty alleviation and sustainable agriculture, particularly among farmers in developing countries Nigeria. Although marketing is important, farmers still find it difficult to participate in markets, especially when faced with pressures from market liberalization (government regulation and restriction). Generally, very few farmers participate in formal markets.

[18]Ogbanje et al. (2016) showed that ineffective marketing channels and poor market information were among factors affecting commercialisation of agriculture. Furthermore, [11]Emana and Gebremedhin (2017) in their study on market chain analysis argued that the marketing of fresh tomato was adversely affected by inadequate marketing facilities, inadequate capacity of local markets to absorb supply, excess of intermediaries, and poor marketing channels. Marketing facilities such as transportation facilities, communication facilities and storage facilities involve cost and thus can affect marketing efficiency and profitability

[4]Adenegan et al. (2013) found that lengthy marketing channels result to low net return and profitability. [18]Ogbanje et al. (2016) also reported that post-harvest losses resulted from insufficient market availability. Where great research effort has been concentrated on output component, especially in the developing countries like Nigeria. However, the challenge of post-harvest losses that account for food insecurity has not received adequate research efforts. It follows that efforts geared towards reducing post-harvest losses will increase fresh tomato availability to consumers and profitability to marketers. Research effort directed at effective management of post-harvest losses of fresh tomato could contribute towards the realization of national objective of tackling food insecurity in Nigeria.

[12]Joseph, et al. (2018) evaluated efficiency of tomato marketing in Loitoktok, and specifically analyzed the structure and conduct of tomato marketing. From the findings, [12]Joseph, et al. (2018) recommended that market actors should have access to soft loans to invest in tomato marketing and reduce market inequalities. [21]Shehu, et al. (2017) study analysed tomato marketing in Kwara State, Nigeria. tomato marketing is a profitable venture in the study area with a average rate of returns to total investment was 52.6%. Also, policies and strategies that lower marketing cost should be vigorously pursued.

[20]Sanusi, and Dada, (2016) study assessed profitability of tomato marketing in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State. with rate of return on investment of 0.35 and 0.21, respectively. [20]Sanusi, and Dada, (2016) recommended that identified constraints be addressed to enhance greater tomato marketing profit in the study area.

Oladejo, and Oladiran, (2014) study analyzed the marketing system and consumption pattern of tomato in Ogbomoso metropolis of Oyo State. Budgetary analysis revealed that tomato marketing is a profitable enterprise with BCR of greater than one.

The tomato industry in Nigeria is very important in driving the economy of the country. It provides means of livelihood to tomato producers, transporters and marketers.

The losses of quality and freshness of the produce is a major source of worry to marketers. Losses could also be due to improper marketing strategies and channels. These losses can therefore lead to decrease in the returns/profitability of the farmers. Literature reviewed that many studies have been conducted on tomatoes and postharvest losses of tomato. [13] Kuranen-Joko & Dzahan (2017) determined the factors affecting postharvest losses in tomato. Achoja and Okoh (2014) reported postharvest properties of tomato and effect on its marketing efficiency. [8]Ayandiji, et al. (2011) examine the determinant of Postharvest losses among tomato Farmers with main focus on the factors leading to post harvest losses among tomato farmers. [19]Sablani, et al. (2016) examine the Influence of bruises and storage temperature on tomato quality and market value. [16]Naika, et al. (2015) studied the cultivation of tomatoes' production, processing and marketing. From the literatures above, it can be concluded that less or no study has been carried out on the effect of marketing channel on post-harvest loses profitability thus, significance of this study. This study has proffered solution to post-harvest wastage. The study is also benefit to fresh tomato marketers in Nigeria, as it will help them maximize profit.

Analyzing the effects of post-harvest losses on the profitability of fresh tomato marketers in Delta state, Nigeria is a critical research puzzle. It is against this background that this study was designed to achieve the following objectives. The specific objectives are to:

- i. describe the marketing channel of fresh tomato
- ii. ascertain the extent of postharvest losses of tomato marketing
- iii. estimate the profitability in tomato marketing
- iv. determine the relationship between marketing channel and post-harvest losses.
- v. determine the effect of post-harvest spoilage on the profitability of tomato marketer in Delta State, Nigeria
- vi. examine the effect of post-harvest losses on the efficiency of fresh tomato Delta State, Nigeria.

1.4 Hypotheses of the study

Ho_i: Value of post-harvest losses has no significant effect on marketer profitability

Ho_{ii}: Tomato marketing channel has no significant effect on post-harvest loss

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area and Sampling Technique

Delta State, Nigeria was the chosen area of this study. This location was chosen for the study due to the presence of a lot of tomato marketers and consumers in the area. The language and culture is familiar to the researcher. It is convenient and the cost implication for the acquiring data will be minimal. It has an area of 603km² and a population of 150,032 people [2] (Achoja and Okoh, 2014). The people are mainly civil servants, farmers and fishermen. The area lies roughly between latitude 6010N and longitude 6045'E. The area has an average annual rainfall of about 8667mm in the coastal area and 1905mm in the north area. The rainfall is heaviest in July with a short break in August. It has an average temperature range of 39⁰C- 44⁰C. Crops grown include root and tuber crops, cereal (maize and swamp rice) cash crops (palm and rubber) and a variety of vegetables including tomato.

Purposive sampling technique was used for the study as there was no data for the list of tomato marketers in the study area, thus every tomato marketer was considered as a respondent.

Data collection and Data analysis techniques

For the purpose of this study, both qualitative and quantitative data were used. Data for this study were obtained mainly from primary sources. The data collection instrument was questionnaire. A well-structured questionnaire was designed and structured according to the specific objective of the study. Test and Re-test method was used for reliability test of the instrument. The essence of the test was to guarantee that the questionnaire was able to collect the expected information for the study. The questionnaire passed through a validity test which was carried out by the project supervisor. Given both tests it is guaranteed that the questionnaire was able to collect the expected information. Copies of the questionnaire was personally administered and retrieved by the researcher. Only questionnaire copies that were correctly filled were used for computation and data analysis. Out of the 170 copies of questionnaire that were administered, 150 copies were correctly filled by the respondents. The response performance is approximately 83%.

[i] Marketing channel of fresh tomato, as stated in objective 1, was achieved using descriptive statistic (mean, percentage, flow chart).

[ii] Extent of spoilage of fresh tomato as stated in objective 2 was achieved using descriptive statistics. (mean, percentage, frequency table).

[iii] The relationship between marketing channel and post-harvest losses was achieved using pearson product moment correlation model.

[iv] The profitability in tomato marketing was achieved using Gross margin model.

[v] The effect of postharvest spoilage on the profitability of tomato marketing was achieved using multiple regression.

[vi] The efficiency of fresh tomato marketing was achieved using the shepherd futrell efficiency model.

Model specification

Model 1: Multiple Regression

The model regression equation was implicitly specified as: $GM=F(X_s)$

The model was explicitly specified and tried in three different functional forms namely linear form semi-log and double log function forms. The functional form with the best fit was chosen as the lead model based on the statistical and economic criteria such as the R^2 , number of significant variables and the F- ratio.

i. Linear form

$$GM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AGE + \beta_2 EDU + \beta_3 HHS + \beta_4 MEXP + \beta_5 VPHS + \beta_6 VTD + \beta_7 CHT + \mu$$

ii. Semi log

$$GM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log AGE + \beta_2 \log EDU + \beta_3 \log HHS + \beta_4 \log MEXP + \beta_5 \log VPHS + \beta_6 \log VTD + \beta_7 \log CHT + \mu.$$

iii. Double log

$$\text{Log Gm} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log \text{AGE} + \beta_2 \log \text{EDU} + \beta_3 \log \text{HHS} + \beta_4 \log \text{MEXP} + \beta_5 \log \text{VPHS} + \beta_6 \log \text{VTD} + \beta_7 \log \text{CHT} + \mu$$

GM= dependent variable
 β_0 =constant.
 $\beta_1 - \beta_7$ = co-efficient of regression for the dependent variable

Table 1: Description of symbol in the multiple regression equation

Variable Symbol	Description	Measurement	A priori Expectation
GM	Gross-margin	Naira	
AGE	AGE	Years	-ve
EDU	Education	Years	-ve
HHS	Household size	Numbers	+ve
MEXP	Marketing Experience	Years	+ve
VPHL	Value of Post-Harvest losses	Naira	-ve
VTD	Volume Traded	Kg	+ve
CHT	Channel Type	Likert Scale of 1- 4 points	-ve
$\beta_1 - \beta_7$	Co-efficient of parameter estimate		
β_0	Constant		
μ	Stochastic Error term		

Model 2: Gross Margin Analysis

The gross margin analysis was used as a proxy for the determination of the profitability in tomato marketing. Gross Margin was used instead of net profit because the total fixed cost (TFC) in tomato marketing is negligible.

Gross margin is expressed mathematically as follows:

$$\text{GM} = \text{TR} - \text{TMVC} \quad \text{where the value of TFC is}$$

GM= Gross margin

TR=Total Revenue

T_mVC = Total marketing variable cost.

Model 3: Shepherd Futrell model

$$\text{ME} = \text{TMC} / \text{TMR} \times 100/1$$

Where ME= marketing efficiency

TMC= Total marketing cost

TMR = total marketing revenue

Shepherd Frutrell model shows the proportion of total revenue swallowed up by marketing cost [2] (Achoja and Okoh,2014).

Decision Rule:

The higher the value of shepherd Futrells' coefficient, the lower the marketing efficiency.

Model 4: Correlation model

The relationship between marketing channel type and post-harvest losses was determined using correlation model as shown below:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Distribution of respondents according to socio-economic characteristics.**

The results of the socio-economic characteristics of tomatoes marketer is presented in table 2. The result shows that majority (97.0%) of the marketers were female with an average age of 42.5 years (Table 2). The implication of this is that most of the respondents were in their active age being able to go about their business with vigour. The household size ranged between 4 and 6 persons with an average of 5 persons. Tables 2 revealed that majority of the marketers were married with the percentage of 53.0%. The respondents' years of experience ranged between 6 and 19 years with an average of 8 years. This indicates that most of the respondents have been involved in tomato marketing for quite a long time. In regards to educational level, the result shows that majority (24%) of the marketers completed their secondary school degree. The result also indicates that 9.0% had no formal education, 18.0% completed primary school, the marketers with OND/NCE and HND/BSC constitute 14.0% and 22.0% respectively. Given this level of literacy, it is expected that information can be disseminated with ease among the respondents. Most (51.0%) of the respondents does not belonged to one cooperative society or the other. Cooperatives are a vehicle for development since they provide informal credit to farmers. Members of the cooperative, *ceteris paribus*, are likely to perform better than non-members because of possible economies of scale. Lastly, Table 2 shows that majority (93.0%) of the respondents were full time marketers in the study area.

Table 2 Distribution of respondents according to socio-economic characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage	Mean/Mode
SEX			
Male	3	3.0	Female
Female	97	97.0	
Age			
<30 years	11	11.0	42.52
31 - 41 years	23	23.0	
42 - 52 years	55	55.0	
above 52 years	11	11.0	
Household size			
1 - 3 persons	14	14.0	
4 - 6 persons	47	47.0	
7 - 9 persons	33	33.0	
above 9 persons	6	6.0	
Marital Status			
Single	16	16.0	Married
Married	53	53.0	
Divorced	11	11.0	
Widow	19	19.0	
Widower	1	1.0	
Educational level			

No formal	9	9.0	
Primary	18	18.0	
Junior secondary school	12	12.0	
Senior secondary school	24	24.0	Secondary school
OND/NCE	14	14.0	
HND/B.Sc	22	22.0	
post graduate	1	1.0	
Membership of cooperative			
No	51	51.0	
Yes	49	49.0	
Mode of Operation			
Full time	93	93.0	Full time
Part time	7	7.0	
Marketing experience			
1 - 5 years	35	35.0	
6 - 10 years	42	42.0	6-10years/7.7
11 - 15 years	17	17.0	
above 15 years	6	6.0	

Field Survey, (2022)

Marketing channels of Tomatoes

The result of marketing channels of tomatoes is presented in Table 3. The result shows that the major channels of tomato marketing in the study area which include buying directly from farmers, wholesalers, retailers, buying in small quantity and marketing from personal tomato farm. The result indicates that majority (66.0%) of the respondents buy tomato from wholesalers while 21.0% purchased from retailers. Those that buy directly from farmers constitute 9.0% while 3.0% of the respondents bought smaller quantity of tomatoes to reduced postharvest wastage. The result implies that wholesalers dominate the marketing channels in the study area. This agrees with the findings of [2]Achoja and Okoh, (2014) who discovered wholesale marketing of tomatoes as marketing channel. They found that wholesalers play major role in marketing of vegetables.

Table 3. Marketing channels of Tomatoes

Channels	Frequency		Percentage	
	No	Yes	No	Yes
Buying directly from farmers	91	9	91.0	9.0
Buying from wholesalers	34	66	34.0	66.0
Buying from retailer	79	21	79.0	21.0
Buying in small quantity	97	3	97.0	3.0
A tomato farmer	99	1	99.0	1.0

Bar Chart showing Distribution of tomato marketing channels

Furthermore, the flow of marketing channels identified in the study shows that 71.0% of the respondents were familiar with producer-wholesalers-retailer and to consumer marketing flow of tomatoes. Also, 22.0% of the respondents were familiar with producer-large retailer and to consumer while 6.0% were familiar with producer-retailer and to consumer.

Figure 1 Bar Chart of marketing channels

Relationship between marketing channel type and post-harvest losses

The result of the correlation analysis presented in Table 4 indicates that there was positive and significant relationship ($p \leq 0.05$) between marketing channels and quantity of tomatoes spoilage while cost of spoilage indicated a positive and significant relationship ($p \geq 0.05$) with marketing channels of tomatoes in the study area. The result also shows that there was a positive and significant ($p \geq 0.05$) relationship between quantity of spoilage and cost of tomatoes spoilage.

The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between marketing channel and postharvest losses is thus rejected and the alternative which states that there is a significant relationship is accepted.

Table 4 Relationship between marketing channel type and post-harvest losses

	Channels	Quantity Of Spoilage	Cost Of Spoilage
CHANNELS Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1	.384** .000	.129 .200
QUANTITY OF SPOILAGE Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)		1	.157 .119
COST OF SPOILAGE Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)			1 0.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5. Profitability in Fresh Tomato Marketing

Cost Items	Amount (₦)	% of total revenue
Tomatoes procurement	31,300.00	69.02
Transport	6,662.00	14.7
Communication	259.30	0.57
Market dues	278.50	0.61
Packaging	0.00	0.00
Levy/rent	1,927.00	4.25
Interest	409.50	0.90
Total cost	40,836.30	
Value of post-harvest losses	13,605.60	30
Expected Revenue (without product losses)	58,989.60	
Actual Revenue (with product losses)	45,352.00	
Profit(gross margin)	4,515.70	
Return to investment	0.11(11.1%)	

Shepherd Futrell's Efficiency Model = $TC/TR \times 100/1$

$$40,836/45,352 \times 100/1 = 90.04\%$$

According to Shepherd futrell coefficient the result in Table 5 indicates that about 90% of total revenue was swallowed up by cost of marketing and post harvest spoilage in the study area. The result indicates low marketing efficiency. This could be due to 30% of revenue (₦13,605.60) lost to product spoilage, fresh tomato spoilage amount have led to the low rate of return on investment. The 30.0% value of post-harvest losses in this study is in agreement with the findings of [2]Achoja and Okoh, (2014) who reported postharvest losses of vegetables to be 20%-30% of volume traded.

Effect of postharvest losses and other variables on the profitability of fresh tomato marketing

Table 5 shows the result of multiple regression of the effect of postharvest losses and marketing channel on the profitability of fresh tomato marketing in the study area. The model was explicitly specified and tried in three different functional forms namely; linear form, semi-log and double log forms. The functional form with the best fit was chosen as the lead model based on statistical and economic criteria such as the R^2 value, number of significant variables and the F-ratio.

From Table 5, the value of R^2 is 0.55. R^2 is the coefficient of multiple determination. This means that the independent variables that are included in this model explained approximately (55%) variation in profitability of fresh tomato marketing in the study area.

The result presented in Table 6 shows that out of the 8 exogenous variables entered in the model, 3 were significant. They are household size (HS), value of postharvest losses (VPHL) and volume traded (VT) by tomato marketer

Household size

In regards to household size the variable entered in the model shows a negative sign and it's significant at $p \leq 0.05$. This implies that an increase the household size will lead to decrease in the profitability of tomato marketing.

Value of post-harvest losses

Value of post-harvest losses shows a negative sign and its significance at $p \leq 0.05$. The result in Table 6 indicates that increase in value of post-harvest losses will lead to decrease in the profitability of tomato marketing. The null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between postharvest losses and profitability is thus rejected and the alternative which states that there is a significant relationship is accepted.

Volume traded

Also, VTD indicates a negative sign and its significance at $p \leq 0.05$. The result implies that increase in value of VTD will lead to decrease in the profitability of tomato marketing.

Table 6. Effect of postharvest losses and other variables on the profitability of fresh tomato marketing

Variables	Linear	Semi-log	Double-log
Constant	23048.118	68686.698	8.591
AGE	-1.48(-1.104)	-0.041(-0.264)	0.200(-0.897)
EDU	0.137(1.751)	0.095(1.140)	0.068(-0.562)
HHS	-0.170(-2.077)**	-0.165(-2.004)**	-0.286(-2.389)**
MKT EXP	0.071(0.545)	0.021(0.139)	0.203(0.955)
VPHL	-0.282(-3.063)***	-0.525(-4.042)***	-0.408(2.716)***
VTD	-0.570(-6.191)***	-0.230(-1.722)	-1.21(-0.752)
CHT	-0.091(-1.259)	0.024(0.314)	0.040(0.381)
R^2	54.5%(0.545)	50.9%(0.509)	23.9%(0.239)
R ADJ	0.510	0.470	0.243
F	15.715(0.000)***	13.304(0.000)***	4.390(0.000)***

NB: The values in parenthesis are the corresponding T values.

** = significant at 5%

*** = significant at 1%

CONCLUSION

The study focused on the analysis of the effect of marketing channel on post-harvest losses and profit level of tomato marketer in Delta State, Nigeria. The motivation for the study was derived from the fact that tomato marketing is a means of livelihood to many people in Delta State, Nigeria. Researching on tomato marketing losses could bring about more profit and thus better livelihoods of the marketers.

On the basis of the research findings, the following conclusions were drawn;

- i) Tomato marketing is a business dominated by young women on full time basis to earn a living.
- ii) It was evident that post-harvest losses was up to 30% of the volume stocked/traded, This is capable of discouraging investment in fresh tomato marketing.
- iii) Fresh tomato spoilage was traced to the long marketing channel operated by marketers, long duration of the product at the shop before sale and high quantity of fresh tomato stocked/traded at a time.
- iv) There was sufficient evidence to conclude that post-harvest spoilage must have been responsible for the low return on investment (ROI) and low efficiency in fresh tomato marketing.
- v) Since profit is the reward for performing marketing functions and for risk-taking, post-harvest losses becomes an issue of major concern to sustainable investment decision in fresh tomato marketing in Delta State, Nigeria.

The following recommendations are made from the study:

1. It is recommended that small scale marketers should reduce the volume of fresh tomato stocked/ traded at a time to reduce spoilage.
2. Fresh tomato marketers should operate short marketing channels in order to minimize distance travelled before the product gets to the store in order to reduce postharvest losses/spoilage.
3. The fresh tomato marketers should reduce consumption by household except it is paid for.
4. Given the dominance of women in the tomato marketing business, Government should organize empowerment programmes for young women on efficient marketing of fresh tomato.

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